

INFLUENCE OF NOTCH GEOMETRY ON BENDING FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF TWILL E-GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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Abstract

An experimental program is designed to study the effect of notch geometry on bending fatigue behavior of Twill E-glass/epoxy composite. Standard specimens and specimens with different type of notches geometry such as circular holes, transverse ellipse, longitudinal ellipse and rectangular slot, have been prepared from plates and are considered for the study.

Displacement-controlled bending fatigue tests with R (stress ratio) of 0.10 were conducted and damage in the composite was continuously monitored through the decrement of bending moment during cycling. Besides, some set of specimens were subjected to 45% of the material ultimate flexural strength, tests were interrupted at 1 million cycles, residual properties were measured and compared with virgin specimen properties of both corresponding geometry and of other notched geometry.

Finally, it is found that notched geometry specimens respond differently due to the variation of radius of curvature at the critical loading section of the notch, besides it is observed that smooth curvature transitions improve the fatigue strength.

1 Introduction

In recent years, extensive research and development has been conducted with the aim of applications, fatigue loading is unavoidable and it is one of the main causes for failure of dynamically loaded component. Therefore, recent designs do not specify the mechanical properties

of advanced composite materials without performing detailed fatigue analysis. One of the major areas of such studies involves notch sensitivity of composite laminates, as notches significantly deteriorate component fatigue performance.

Composite materials are getting more and more popular in almost all engineering disciplines, so today it is a common trend to use this group of material as a primary load carrying structural members in many applications. In such applications, the desired structural integrity or load path is obtained through assembly of individual structural components by using different mechanical joining techniques. The two commonly used joining techniques are mechanically fastened joint and adhesively bonded joints and these two techniques have been widely used separately or combined [1]. Although, each joining techniques has its own special advantages and drawbacks, when relatively thick structures are used and designed to withstand high levels of loads in service life, or component disassembly is required for inspection and repair purposes, mechanically fastened joining, like bolted and rivet joints are usually preferred. However, this type mechanical fastener is not a preferred joining method, as drilling holes in composites reduce the strength, through fibre breakage and the consequence stress concentration, but drilling holes on structure is unavoidable, since some structural integrity cannot be obtain by other means. Besides, hole in structural laminate can serve as access area of any purpose, including lubrication, pneumatic and hydraulic lines. Therefore, to minimize the loss of fatigue strength due to fibre breakage and stress

concentration resulted by notches, and to reduce the consequent adoption of higher safety factors, that affects both cost and weight in the component, extensive study and clear understanding on the area are needed.

Relatively speaking, today there is some general Consensus on composite fatigue performance and it is well understood that, failure of FRC under fatigue loading is more complicated than metals due to their anisotropic characteristics in both strength and stiffness. In fact, the heterogeneous and anisotropic nature of FRC leads to the formation of different stress levels within the material, so that the fracture processes includes various combinations of damage modes like matrix cracking, fibre breakage, delamination, debonding and ply failure. Moreover, voids and defects contained in FRC matrix can act as sites for nucleation of fatigue failure [1-5]. In general, the sequence of fatigue damage in all materials can be summarized within three stages: crack initiation, crack propagation and crack separation. In conventional metallic material like steel and aluminium, much of the life is spent before crack appears; however, once a crack forms, it propagates rapidly and the material fails. In contrast, for composite materials, cracks nucleate within a few numbers of cycles even at lower stress levels and most of the life is spent after cracks appear [4].

The degradation evolution in bending fatigue tests as function of number of cycles can be expressed as the relative reduction in elastic modulus [5] or as relative changes in bending moment [2, 4].

Wide open literatures are available on the bending fatigue behaviour of notched and un-notched fibre reinforced composite (FRC). Van Paepegem W. and Degrieck J [6,7] conduct experimental and simulation bending fatigue study on un-notched plain glass/epoxy composite material and identified the three stages of stiffness degradation i.e. an initial sharp decline associated with the formation of "damage zones", which contain microscopic cracks and other forms of damage, such as fibre/matrix interface failure and pull-out of fibres from the matrix; a second stage of very gradual deterioration of the material which is characterized by a gradual reduction of the stiffness; a third and final stage associated with material failure with more serious types of damage, such as fibres fracture and instable delamination growth. Belingardi et al. [2] conduct a detail Material characterization and bending fatigue property study of relatively complex un-notched intraply hybrid composite that consists of

distinct layers of biaxial glass-fibre-reinforced composite and biaxial carbon fibre-reinforced composites as well as biaxial layers of bundles of carbon and glass fibres mixed within a single layer and final provide an important information about the targeted material for design purpose and observed that the amount of stiffness reduction was a function of the magnitude of applied fatigue loading. To clarify the effect of mean stress on the behaviour of the S-N diagram, M. H. Abd Allah et al [5], conduct a constant deflection flexural fatigue tests on standard unidirectional glass fibre reinforced polyester (GFRP) composite pultruded rods and found that, mean stress has a slight effect on the material constant (slope of the S-N power function). Similarly R. A. Abeles Couillard, P. Schwartz [8], Conduct a bending fatigue material characterization of unidirectional, continuous-carbon-fibre/epoxy composite and the found that at high strains, damage occurred through fibre breakage, matrix cracking, and interfacial shear failure and for given radius of curvature and up to 10E6 cycles, the loss in bending moment followed an exponential decay. Herrington and Doucet [9] conduct a bending fatigue test on notched glass-epoxy composites. Setting failure criterion of 15% drop in applied moment they identify the three stage of composite failure and they did also made Visual observations and identified that fibre breakage and matrix cracking occurs rapidly in the early stages of the test. The same author, Conduct a bending fatigue test on spring orientation glass fibre reinforced epoxy with circular hole of two different hole diameter/specimen width ratios and they conclude that reduction in stiffness during fatigue cycling was linearly related to the total delamination size, independent of the maximum applied load and determined that the relative size of the hole had no significant effect on the bending fatigue life.

In the present work, an experimental program is designed to study the effect of notch geometry on bending fatigue behaviour of Twill E-glass/epoxy composite. Standard specimens and specimens with different type of notches geometry, such as circular holes, transverse ellipse, longitudinal ellipse and rectangular slot, have been prepared from plates and are considered for the study.

2 Manufacturing process of specimens

The material under investigation is a prepreg (twill 2X2 type) E-glass/epoxy composite with a mass of 250 g/m² and resin mass content of 36.5% and its mechanical property is presented in table

1. It was supplied by Umeco plc, England, and used by EXP s.r.l, Italy. The resin matrix type is epoxy resin developed for automotive sector. It is characterized by good impact resistance properties, quality surface finish and in particular adapted for high speed cold stamping. Fourteen prepreg layers were stacked together in order to obtain the laminate with lay-up of $[0/90]_{14}$.

To be more economical and reliable in preparation of test specimens, special attention had been given to selection of appropriate mould material that can be reused. Dimensional stability at high temperature and chemical compatibility with specimen materials were the main factors to choose epoxy resin block as a mold. To achieve high grade surface finishing, the moulds were cleaned with Chem Cleaner after machining process in order to remove all traces of solvent-soluble contaminants such as waxes, silicones, oils, etc. Then after, Chemlease® MPP 712 EZ which acts as a sealant was used to coat the surface of moulds and cured for about 3 hours at room temperature. After the mould was cured, Chemlease® mold release was applied to assist easy removal of the finished laminate from the mould. At this stage, plies were cut from prepreg e-glass/epoxy fabric and assigned in inside the mold according to desired stacking sequence.

To avoid voids and entrapped air inside wet prepeg, the mould was covered with vacuum plastic bag and subjected to vacuum pressure of 0.98 bar. Then the specimens were transferred to autoclave to apply appropriate controlled pressure and temperature with desired curing cycle. The Vacuum bagging, autoclave used and the specimen considered for the study are shown on Fig 1 and 2.

During the initial stage, the mould containing moulded specimens were subjected to pressure of 3 bars under temperature of 126°C for one hour. Simultaneously, vacuum pressure was applied to the mould to further enhance removal of voids and entrapped air from prepreg specimens. For the next 4 hours the mould was subjected to 126°C with ambient pressure to get the required curing cycle. Finally, it was taken out from the autoclave and exposed to room temperature for some times until mould temperature gets down to the surrounding temperature. With appropriate tools, the laminate was extracted from the mould and ready for further process.

It is worth to specify the thickness of wet prepreg specimen, before polymerization, and the final one, after curing, which were 3.5mm and 2.5mm, respectively. These results emphasize how it is

very essential to know the nature of composite material prior to polymerization to decide the dimensional allowance to get desired component size.

In general, the manufacturing process gives quality product with insignificant defects such as resin poor regions and voids due to trapped air, which were observed clearly during post failure analysis of specimens.

One of critical steps in producing composite structures having mechanical joints such as holes is to drill holes. This process requires multidisciplinary design consideration from cutting parameter to cooling systems to avoid specimen damage during machining process. So, in this work, a great effort has been dedicated to implement the best experience proposed by different scholars.

3 Test procedures

In order to study the effect of notch geometry on the static flexural loading and since our testing program includes static flexural tests on pre-cycled specimens, four-point static flexural tests, with stroke rate 1.3 mm/min as per ASTM standard, see figure 3, were conducted using the same specimen geometry of bending fatigue tests. The test was performed on universal testing machine that has maximum loading capacity of 100 kN. However, considering the failure load levels of the material under study, a 10 kN load cell was mounted on the testing machine to improve measurement accuracy of the applied load. The distance between the inner bearings was set at 16 mm, while the distance between the outer bearings was set at 65 mm.

Having static flexural result, displacement controlled four-point bending fatigue tests with stress ratio (R) of 0.1 were performed on Schenk-type bending fatigue machine, the test set up and mechanical scheme are shown in Fig. 4 and 5 respectively. The tests were conducted at room temperature and at a frequency of 10Hz. For the scope of this testing campaign, the machine was instrumented with a LVDT transducer, placed at the end of the measure lever (on the left in Fig. 5), that allows to continuously monitor the displacement during cycling. Data of the lever displacement were acquired by an acquisition unit, filtered to remove the effect of noise and then stored on a PC. Through the calibration curve of the helical spring at the base of the measure lever, measured data of the lever deflection were converted into values of the bending moment applied on the specimen. Therefore, stiffness degradation is evaluated by measuring bending

moment reduction and elaborating these results as Relative Bending Moment (RBM) Eq. 1, also called dynamic modulus:

$$RBM = \frac{BM_N}{BM_1} \quad (1)$$

Where,

BM_N – Bending Moment at the N-th cycle

BM_1 Bending Moment at the first cycle

To develop standard S-N curves, where data points correspond to specimen failure, of the material under study and for this particular loading condition, the experimental fatigue testing was carried out at five different initial stress levels. In particular, the level of the maximum stress in the first cycle was taken as a percentage of the average ultimate flexural strength (UFS), as obtained in the static flexural tests

After the fatigue tests were interrupted, static flexural tests were run on the pre-cycled specimens that survived to 1 million cycle i.e. specimen loaded at 45% of UFS, to measure the material residual flexural strength and residual flexural modulus. Test procedure for measurement of the residual properties is the same as that for measurement of the ultimate properties on virgin specimens.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Four point static flexural test

Results of static four point flexural test, for five different notch geometry are presented in Fig 6 and sample of failed specimen from each geometry type are presented in Fig 7. From each type of notch geometries, five specimens have been tested in the same loading condition. It is observed that, when a notched composite plate subjected to static flexural loading, failure is mainly governed by local effect i.e. the presence of local defect like stress concentration point leads a significant strength reduction.

Comparing the geometries under investigation, minimum strength with large standard deviation is observed on rectangular slot specimen and maximum strength with small standard deviation is obtained on specimen with longitudinal elliptical slot. This is due to the fact that, a sharp curvature change in the rectangular slot geometry (red marked), cause higher stress concentration that leads higher strength loss on the plate. Specimen with longitudinal elliptical slot has relatively higher notch dimension than circular and transverse elliptical slots, i.e. high material amount are removed from the plate but still it perform better than both. Therefore, when an

opening is needed on flexural loaded components for some purpose, more emphasise have to be given to the notch geometry and the direction of loading that the component will exposed than the size of the notches. With the similar reasoning, comparing circular and transverse elliptical slot, which have almost similar circumference area, circular notch gives slight higher strength value and lower standard deviations. Comparing longitudinal elliptical slot with circular and transversal elliptical slot, longitudinal elliptical slot again yield higher flexural strength value resulted from higher radiuses of curvature along the load axis.

4.2 Four point bending fatigue test

A representative curve that explains how stiffness gradually reduces with number of cycle and how composite material behaves differently with respect to conventional metallic material is presented in Fig 8. As discussed by a number of researchers, when a composite material is subjected to fatigue loading, there are three distinct stages of stiffness degradation. At first, there is relatively higher rate of stiffness degradation within the first few hundred cycles (region A), due to the presence of different manufacturing fault, like void and some other micro defects, which is then followed by a very slow gradual stiffness degradation that covers a large portion of component life (region B) and the third stage (region C), is the stage where more serious types of damage such as fibres fracture, that leads a complete material failure, will takes place.

As our study ultimately is aimed to develop a S-N curve for this particular material, type of loading and set of geometries, a representative curve for a selected geometry (circular geometry) that explains how different percentage of AFL affect both the rate of stiffness reduction with number of cycle and the life of the component is presented on Fig 9 (where, each curve is an average of four tests). Obviously, loading the component with higher percentage of failure load will reduce the service life and for this particular case, the specimen can survive up to 1 million cycles when it is loaded less than 50% of AFL.

Comparing the five geometry under investigation at the same loading (70% AFL), as it is clearly shown in Fig 10, unlike static flexural loading, discussed above, for the case of fatigue flexural loading, even if local defects like stress concentration has its own contribution, failure is manly influenced by the cumulative damage on the overall surface of the specimen. Drilling is an

operation which in most cases introduces loads along the weakest direction (perpendicular on the fiber directions and inter-ply interface) and furthermore, the loads act differently on each ply during the process causing internal damage. The accumulation of those fatigue damage around holes or notches in a composite material yields at least three matrix-dominated cracking and they do interact too. The propagation of a transverse ply matrix crack will interact with an adjacent fiber-matrix interfacial crack. Delamination between layers or plies is affected by splitting in neighboring layers. In addition, the ends of broken fibers act as stress concentrators and affect the nucleation sites and multiplication of further matrix cracks that also act as stress concentrators [1]. This split fibers and edge delaminations together with other micro defects will be the source of crack nucleation and multiplication when the component is under fatigue loading, which ultimately accelerates material degradation. Therefore, the larger the dimension of the hole produced the larger splitting of the fibers and edge delaminations. Therefore, due to higher probability of having larger number of manufacturing defects during removing higher portion of the specimen and wider damage area, specimen with the notch geometry such as, longitudinal elliptical slot, rectangular slot and standard specimen (due to the necking at the centre) show reduced fatigue life. Particularly, rectangular slot gives the worst fatigue performance due to the cumulative effect of stress concentration and larger damage zone.

Standard S-N curve for the five notch geometries under investigation, for this particular material and loading case are presented in Fig 11, where each data point is an average of four test specimens and corresponds to the failure of the specimen with the respective stress.

Observing the steeper part of the curve, specimens with a notch geometry rectangular slot, standard spacemen and longitudinal ellipse show an early failure at higher percentage of AFL within a few hundred cycles respectively, whereas specimens with a notch of circular and transversal ellipse shows relatively better performance. Final, fatigue tests were conducted for some set of specimens loaded at 45% AFL. The tests were interrupted at 1 million cycles; and the residual properties were measured using the same static flexural test set up as virgin specimen. The result of pre-cycled and the corresponding virgin specimen is presented on table 2 and a sample of load-deflection curve of

specimen with circular hole for virgin and pre-cycled specimen is presented in Fig 12

5 Conclusions

An exhaustive experimental investigation were conducted on both four point static flexural strength and four point bending fatigue behaviour of E-glass/epoxy composite material with five different notch geometries. The result can be summarized as follow.

- In general, when a composite material is subjected to fatigue loading, there are three distinct stages of stiffness degradation. Initially, there is relatively higher rate of stiffness degradation within the first few hundred cycles due to the presence of different manufacturing defects, like void and some other micro defects. Then very slow gradual stiffness degradation follows which covers a large portion of component life and finally more serious types of damage such as fibres fracture that leads a complete material failure will takes place.
- When a composite material with a notch is subjected to static flexural load, the performance is mainly influenced by the presence of stress concentration and the direction of loading than the size of the notch. A higher radius of curvature perpendicular the load direction results in higher flexural strength.
- Conversely, when notched composite material is subjected to bending fatigue loading, the performance is mainly governed by the size of the notch. As well known, fatigue failure of composite material is mainly due to the cumulative damage on the overall surface of the specimen than local damage. Therefore, as the size of the notch increases, there will be a higher probability of having larger number of manufacturing defects that result in reduced fatigue life.

6 References

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7 Figures and Tables.

Fig.1. Laminate production: Vacuum bagging and autoclave.

Fig.2. specimen considered for the study.

Fig.3. Static Four-point flexural test setup.

Fig.4. Four-point bending fatigue tests setup

Fig.5. mechanical scheme of four-point bending fatigue tests

Fig.6. Static Flexural strength results for selected geometries in MPa.

Fig.7. Failure mode of static flexural test

Fig.8. Three distinct stiffness reduction zone

Fig.9. Fatigue response of specimen with circular notch at different AFL

Fig.10. Fatigue performance of five notch geometry at 70%AFL

Fig.11. S-N curve for the five notch geometries.

Fig.12. Load-deflection curve of specimen with circular hole for virgin and pre-cycled specimen

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the material under investigation

Composite type	0/90E-Glass/Epoxy
Weave	2x2 Twill
Fiber fraction (Wt %)	0,63.4
Tensile strength (MPa)	496,62±4,98
E_x (GPa)	25,488 (0,17)
G_{xy} (GPa)	3, 543 (0,059)
ν_{xy}	0,126 (0,009)

Note. Values in parentheses are standard deviations

Table 2 Flexural strength for virgin and pre-cycle specimen

Notch Geometry	Flexural strength (Mpa)		% of Strength reduced
	virgin Specimen	pre-cycle	
Circular Hole	540.4	454.065	16
Transverse Ellipse	538.38	430.5	20
Long. Ellipse	565.66	392.05	30.7
Rectangular slot	525.922	350.79	33.3